

eliminating the risk of somaclonal variation in successive subcultures. A logical extension of the rate of multiplication through successive cultures should yield 1×5^n axillary shoots, where n is the number of subcultures, with each cycle requiring 3-4 wk. Since rooting is essential to establish the shoots in soil, an additional cycle on MS medium supplemented with root-inducing auxin NAA at 1.5 mg/liter may be necessary. □

Tissue culture for Argentine rice (*O. sativa* L.) improvement

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Seeds of Argentine rice varieties Yerua F.A. and Gualeyan P.A. were cultured on Murashige and Skoog's (MS) basic salts supplemented with 2 mg 2,4-D/liter of medium in darkness at 28 °C. Callus formed 15 d after inoculation. Callus induction was 100% in both varieties.

Calli were subcultured on a regeneration medium with the same basic salts supplemented with 1 mg BAP/liter. Plant regeneration was 30% in Yerua, 50% in Gualeyan.

The plantlets were transferred to pots containing sterile vermiculite and watered with 1/4 MS salts. After 1 wk, they were transplanted to the greenhouse and grown to maturity. Seeds were obtained from all the plants, although fertility was not 100%.

Seeds from the regenerated plants and seeds from the original varieties were planted at 20- × 20-cm spacing and conventional cultivation procedures followed. At maturity, sample plants were collected to evaluate agronomic traits; the rest were used for testing yield characteristics and blast resistance.

The first progeny of plants regenerated from Gualeyan (R_2) showed higher tillering ability than the original variety; 20% had a different husk color.

Table 1. Variation among the first progeny of Gualeyan P. A. regenerated plants (R_2) and progeny of the original variety. Buenos Aires, Argentina, 1987.

Trait	Gualeyan	R_2 progeny		<i>F</i> test ^a
		Mean	Range	
Panicle length (cm)	17.66	22.08	12.09-25.6	**
Grain with husk				
Length (mm)	9.35	9.13	8.5 - 9.85	**
Width (mm)	3.82	3.52	4.0 - 3.0	**
Grain without husk				
Length (mm)	7.11	7.78	6.3 - 1.85	**
Width (mm)	3.11	2.89	2.5 - 3.15	**

^a*** = significant at 1% level.

Table 2. Variation among the first progeny of Yerua F. A. regenerated plants (R_2) and progeny of the original variety. Buenos Aires, Argentina, 1987.

Trait	Yerua	R_2 progeny		<i>F</i> test ^a
		Mean	Range	
Panicle length (cm)	21.14	22.30	12.3 - 3.0	**
Grain with husk				
Length (mm)	10.34	9.67	11.0 - 6.5	ns
Width (mm)	3.54	3.74	3.25- 4.3	*
Grain without husk				
Length (mm)	7.94	7.51	6.5 - 8.7	*
Width (mm)	3.1	3.04	26.5 - 4.1	**

^aSignificant at 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels.

Panicle length and two grain dimensions—with and without husk—also significantly differed (Table 1). The first progeny of plants regenerated from Yerua (R_2) showed low plant height and significant differences for panicle length, grain width with husk, and grain length

without husk (Table 2).

This study showed a definite trend toward more somaclonal variation in Gualeyan than in Yerua. The tissue culture-derived plants may be useful as sources of new germplasm. □

Morphoanatomy of rice embryo development

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Histological studies of cultured embryos during the early stages of cell proliferation provide information about the initial sites and patterns of cell division activity and subsequent differentiation. Morphological observations through the scanning electron microscope (SEM) provide a clear picture of the natural concave-convex appearance of the various stages of embryoid development.

Dehulled mature seeds of rice variety Tetep were sterilized and inoculated in Linsmaier and Skoog's (LS) medium, each liter containing 1 mg 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) gelled with 1% agar. Cultures were maintained in darkness at 26-27 °C.

The scutella were isolated from embryos still embedded in the seed after 1 wk in culture. Samples for histological and SEM analysis were taken 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 d after seed inoculation; subsequent samples from subcultures were taken every 4 wk.

For plant regeneration, 3-mo-old calli were transferred to Murashige and Skoog's (MS) medium, each liter containing 4 mg benzylaminopurine